

Spectrophotometric Study of Chelate Formation by Interaction of Hexavalent Chromium and Alizarin Red S

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Formation of a pink-coloured complex by the interaction of Cr (VI) and sodium alizarin-3-sulphonate (Alizarin Red S) has been reported. The chelate has maximum absorption at 515 m μ . The composition, as determined by the method of continued variation using spectrophotometric measurements, is indicated to be 1:1. The chelate is stable between pH 3.5 and 8.0. The stability has been determined by a method described by the authors and the values of logK and ΔF° work out respectively to be 4.72 ± 0.25 and -6.52 ± 0.35 kcal. at 25°.

Sodium alizarin-3-sulphonate, commonly known as Alizarin Red S (abbreviated as ARS), is a member of the anthraquinone series of dyes and yields coloured chelates with various metals (Dey and Mukherji, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 242; Dey and Banerji, *Proc. Symp. Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds*, Agra, 1959). The presence of quinoid oxygen with hydroxyl groups in α and β positions is responsible for its chromophoric properties while the presence of a sulphonate group adds reactivity to the molecule. The structure of the compound is :

(Sodium alizarin-3-sulphonate)

Dey and co-workers studied the chromophoric properties of the reagent in detail and found it useful for the colorimetric determination of uranium (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, 160, 98) and of copper (*Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1958, 31, 521). They also studied the characteristics of aqueous solutions of the reagent and found that the reagent behaved as a colloidal electrolyte (*Kolloid Z.*, 1958, 158, 147). It was emphasised that for physico-chemical measurements, extremely dilute solutions should be employed so as to exhibit the characteristics of a true solution.

In further communications from these laboratories chelate formation of Alizarin Red S with lead (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1957, 26A, 20), copper (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 461), thorium, and hafnium (unpublished) has been reported. Chelates involving the reagent have also been described by Raghava Rao *et al.* (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 79, 142), Leibhatsky and Winslow (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1776), Larsen and Hirozawa (*J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, 3, 198), and by others.

A spectrophotometric method for the determination of formation constants of coloured chelates has been described by Mukherji and Dey (*J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314); the method has an advantage over that of Anderson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195; 1949 71, 909, 912) that it is applicable to systems where one of the interactants may be coloured. In the present communication, formation of the coloured chelates by the interaction of hexavalent chromium and Alizarin Red S has been described.

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EXPERIMENTAL

An aqueous solution of B.D.H. Reagent grade Alizarin Red S was prepared without further purification. The solution was standardised by estimating the sulphur content. B.D.H. AnalaR potassium chromate was used and the concentration was checked by the iodometric method. Solutions were prepared in double distilled water and fresh solutions were used to avoid effects due to hydrolysis.

Spectrophotometric Measurements.—Spectrophotometric studies were done with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer operated by a Dorans Mains unit working on 220v/50 cycles stabilised A.C. mains. Glass measuring cells of 10 mm thickness supplied with the instrument were used. The experiments were performed in an air-conditioned room maintaining $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. The solutions and the mixtures were kept in a Townson and Mercer thermostatic bath maintaining $25^{\circ} \pm 0.01^{\circ}$. The mixtures were kept for 30 minutes, before measurements, in the thermostat to attain equilibrium.

pH measurements were done with the help of L. & N pH indicator, operated by 220v/50 cycles A.C. mains, with a glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode supplied by the same manufacturers. The meter was calibrated with a standard buffer and occasionally checked during measurements.

The maximum absorption of potassium chromate lies at $370 \text{ m}\mu$, that of alizarin red S at $420 \text{ m}\mu$ while a mixture of potassium chromate and the reagent has a maximum absorption at $515 \text{ m}\mu$. This shows the formation of a chelate between the interactants.

Stoichiometry of the Components

The composition was determined by Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928). Measurements using both equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions

FIG. 1

Equimolecular solutions at $515 \text{ m}\mu$ ($p = 1$).

Curve A: $c = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. Curve B: $c = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.
Curve C: $c = 3.33 \times 10^{-4} M$. Curve D: $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$.

FIG. 2

Equimolecular solutions at $525 \text{ m}\mu$ ($p = 1$)

Concentrations the same as in Fig. 1.

in large number (total volume = 50c.c.) were done at two different wave lengths, viz., 515 and 525 $m\mu$. This was necessary to ascertain definitely the composition of the complex (Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437). Some of the typical observations are plotted in Figs. 1-4. In the figures, the difference of absorbance of the mixture and that which would be shown by the chelating agent alone, in case of no reaction (chromate ions have no absorption at the wave lengths of measurement), is plotted against composition of the mixture.

FIG. 3.

Non-equimolecular solutions at 515 $m\mu$.

Curve A: $c = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 0.67$).
 Curve B: $c = 3.33 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 1.5$).
 Curve C: $c = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 2.0$).
 Curve D: $c = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ ($p = 2.0$).

FIG. 4.

Non-equimolecular solutions at 525 $m\mu$.

Concentrations the same
as in Fig. 3.

In the legends to the figures, the concentration of the chromate solution is represented by c , while c' is the concentration of Alizarin Red S; hence $p = c'/c$.

Influence of pH on the Stability of the Chelate

The absorbance of mixtures of $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ potassium chromate and 2.5×10^{-4} Alizarin Red S at different pH was measured at different wave lengths. The results are represented in Fig. 5. It may be seen that the λ_{max} of the mixtures lie at 515 $m\mu$ between pH 3.5 and 8.0, showing that the chelate is stable in this range of pH.

FIG. 5

Influence of pH on absorbance.

The following table records the results on the composition, arrived at from Figs. 1-4, indicating that the composition corresponds to 1 : 1. The table apparently reveals the composition in the case of non-equimolecular solutions also. Thus, it is not possible to calculate the stability from these curves by the method of continued variation.

TABLE I

No. Fig.	Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	μ .	Wave length.	Peak occurring at volume of K_2CrO_4 .	Composition of the chelate $Cr(VI) : ARS$.
1	A	5.00 M	1.0	515 $m\mu$	25.0 c.c.	1:1
	B	4.00	1.0			
	C	3.33	1.0			
	D	2.50	1.0			
2	A	5.00	1.0	525	25.0	Do
	B	4.00	1.0			
	C	3.33	1.0			
	D	2.50	1.0			
3	A	5.00	0.67	515	20.0 30.0 33.3 33.3	Do
	B	3.33	1.50			
	C	2.50	2.00			
	D	2.00	2.00			
4	A	5.00	0.67	525	20.0 30.0 33.3 33.3	Do
	B	3.33	1.50			
	C	2.05	2.00			
	D	2.00	2.00			

The apparent formation constant of the chelate has been calculated from the observed absorbance-composition curves, as described earlier (*this Journal*, 1957, 34, 461). In Fig. 6, in the descending portions of the curves A, B, C, and D, it may reasonably be assumed that the absorbance is due to the colour of the complex alone since chromate ions are colorless at the dilutions and are in excess over the chelating agent, a majority of which therefore is bound up in the complex, which is fairly stable, and does not contribute substantially to the colour of the system. Thus, at concentrations of the reactants in curves A, B, C, and D, where the absorbance is the same (say 0.25), the amounts of the complex formed are identical.

FIG. 6

Formation constant from absorption spectra data at 515 m μ .

In an equilibrium of the type :

where M and Ke are the metal and the chelating agent respectively, x is the concentration of the chelate at equilibrium, and a and b are the initial concentrations of the metal ion and the chelating agent respectively, we have formation constant

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-x)} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

Taking two concentrations having the same absorbance, *i.e.*, the same value of x , we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-x)} = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-x)} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

or

$$x = \frac{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}{(a_1 + b_1) - (a_2 + b_2)} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

Hence from a knowledge of two initial concentrations, a_1 , a_2 and b_1 , b_2 , we can calculate x from (iii). Knowing x , K can be evaluated from (i). The value of $\log K$ in this system works out to be 4.72 ± 0.25 at 25° .

The free energy of formation

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K,$$

where the terms have their usual significance. In $\text{Cr(VI)} - \text{ARS}$ system, ΔF° at 25° is found to be -6.53 ± 0.34 k cal.